

Communication Slice Allocation for Network Slicing - Position Points

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Abstract

The paper explores the AI and machine learning based allocation of communication resources for network slicing. It discusses the latest trends and technologies for resource allocation in the context of network slicing. The paper analyzes the application areas and market trends of network slicing, highlighting the need for optimized resource allocation and communication slice design. It presents a SARSA agent-based approach for interdomain communication slice optimization and emphasizes the importance of SDN as an enabler for network slicing. The paper concludes by proposing position points that can guide future research and development in this field.

Index Terms

Resource Allocation, Network Slicing, Communication Resources, Communication Slice, Machine Learning, Agent Embedding, ML-native Agent, Communication Slice Optimization, Software-defined Networking, Technology Enabler.

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1 OBJECTIVE AND FOCUS

Resource allocation is a relevant problem addressed by research for network slicing and other areas with various perspectives [1] [2].

Resource allocation using artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) algorithms and methods is an actual trend [3] [4] [5].

The allocation of communication resources in terms of communication slices for network slicing is the focus of this document [6] [7].

Objective and Focus

- ◆ To discuss resource allocation and trends for network slicing:

- AI-native resource allocation with machine learning

- ◆ Focus on the intelligent allocation of communication resources

Fig. 1. Objective and Focus

2 INTRODUCTION - THE RESOURCE ALLOCATION CONTEXT AND TREND

There is a huge set of systems and applications with new stringent requirements, such as:

- 5G/6G Next-Generation Mobile Network (NGNM) (5G and 6G) [8];
- The Internet of Things (IoT) [9];
- E-health systems [10];
- Industry 4.0 [11];
- The Internet of Vehicles (IoV) [2]; and
- Other.

On-demand and dynamic resource allocation are currently an absolute must for new systems.

The Resource Allocation Context and Trend

◆ There is a huge set of systems and applications with new stringent requirements:

- 5G/6G next-generation mobile network, the Internet of Things (IoT), e-health systems, industry 4.0, the Internet of Vehicles (IoV), and other

◆ New stringent requirements include:

- On-demand resource allocation
- Dynamic network performance requirements:
 - ◆ Delay, QoS, QoE, SLA, and other
- A large number and variety of distributed and heterogeneous devices
- A highly dynamic traffic pattern
- Various physical topologies
- Other

How to accomplish these new requirements?

Fig. 2. The Resource Allocation Context and Trend

3 WHAT RESOURCES TO ALLOCATE?

There is a broad range of resource types to allocate depending on the system being considered.

Resources, currently, are virtualized to allow a more efficient resource allocation and sharing [12] [13].

Communication resources like communication links, communication slices, and equivalent deployments are the focus of this discussion.

What Resources to Allocate?

- ◆ Computational capacity: Bare Metal, virtual machine (VM), GPU, and other
- ◆ **Communication slice/ communication link: spectrum slot, bandwidth, a virtual private network (VPN), elastic optical network (EON) optical slot, and other**
- ◆ IoT devices: sensor, actuator, ...
- ◆ Cache
- ◆ Virtual network equipment: switch, access point, routing, ...
- ◆ Virtual Network Function (VNF)
- ◆ Virtual Network: network slicing
- ◆ Spectrum Slot: random access network (RAN), 5G/6G context
- ◆ Other

Our focus: the communication link or communication slice

Fig. 3. What Resources to Allocate?

5 MACHINE LEARNING AGENT EMBEDDING

ML agents embedding into systems and applications is a current trend enforcing an AI-native approach [18].

An AI-native approach for network slicing orchestration considering the SFI2 architecture is presented in [19] and AI-native for 6G is discussed in [20].

Machine Learning Agents Embedding

◆ There is a variety of ML algorithms and methods used for resource allocation

- **Supervised ML algorithms:**
 - ◆ Linear Regression and Gradient Descent, K-Nearest Neighbor (KNN), Decision Trees (DT), Random Forest (RF), Support Vector Machines (SVM), and other
- **Unsupervised learning:**
 - ◆ Self-organized maps (SOM), K-means, and other
- **Reinforcement learning:**
 - ◆ Q-Learning, SARSA, and other
- **Deep Learning (DL):**
 - ◆ Hierarchical neural networks (HNN), multilayer perceptrons (MLP), convolution neural network (CNN), recurrent neural networks (RNNs), long short-term memory networks (LSTMs), and generative adversarial networks (GANs), other
- **Neural Networks (NN)**

◆ ML agent embedding is a current trend

Fig. 5. Machine Learning Agents Embedding

6 MACHINE LEARNING RESEARCH ISSUES AND RESOURCE ALLOCATION

Most current machine learning research issues can be explored and visited by concomitantly addressing the resource allocation problem. This is, indeed, a window opportunity for research [21] [22] [17].

Machine Learning Research Issues and the Resource Allocation Context

- ◆ Machine learning, as an area, has its research issues:
 - What is the best-fit ML algorithm to use is a common question with open research issues
 - Where to place ML processing?
 - ◆ At the edge?
 - ◆ Centralized?
 - ◆ Distributed?
 - How to learn?
 - ◆ Centralized, distributed, ...
 - How to model and optimize agents?
 - ◆ Model issues
 - ◆ Multi-agents
 - ◆ Optimization and task offloading
- ◆ Resource allocation and communication resource allocation share common research issues

digwatch, "5G Digital Watch Observatory," 2023. <https://dig.watch/technologies/5g> [accessed Apr. 05, 2023].

Qualcomm, "Distributed Intelligence," 2023. <https://www.qualcomm.com/products/technology/artificial-intelligence/what-is-ai-faq/distributed-intelligence> [accessed Apr. 05, 2023].

Fig. 6. Machine learning research issues and resource allocation

7 NETWORK SLICING AND APPLICATION AREAS

Network slicing is a crucial enabler to support the composition and deployment of virtual network infrastructures required by the dynamic behavior of networks like 5G/6G mobile networks, IoT-aware networks, e-health systems, and industry verticals like the internet of vehicles (IoV) and industry 4.0 [23] [24] [25]. In general, the slicing process results from the need to share resources among existing infrastructures to improve performance, provide cost-efficient solutions, and optimize operation [26].

The network slicing life cycle process is standardized and has phases such as commissioning, operating, and decommissioning. These phases require network communication resources [27] [28] [23].

Network Slicing Concept and Application Areas

- ◆ Network slicing (NS):
 - Network slicing is a new paradigm that allows the composition and deployment of dynamic virtual networks
- ◆ NS application areas:
 - Extensively used in 5G/6G with potential applications in IoT, Internet of Vehicles (IoV), Industry 4.0, and other
- ◆ NS outcome: SLICE or Slice-as-a-Service (SlaaS)
- ◆ On-demand and dynamic virtual networks are created
- ◆ SlaaS composition and deployment is a process with a life cycle:
 - 3GPP NS Life Cycle

3GPP, "Management, Orchestration and Charging for 5G networks," 2023. <https://www.3gpp.org/news-events/3gpp-news/sa5-5g> (accessed Apr. 05, 2023).

Fig. 7. Network Slicing and Application Areas

8 NETWORK SLICING TECHNOLOGY - MARKET AND TRENDS

Network slicing technology’s most relevant market is the Next Generation Mobile Network (NGMN) with 5G and 6G networks. NS provides a slicing service (slice-as-a-Service: SlaaS) for network operators [23].

Deployed network slicing allows 5G/6G customers to create customized virtual networks (slices) tailored to their specific application domains and to develop their own business models [20].

Network slicing is expanding its use in other scenarios of telecommunication networks, content provider networks (ISPs), experimental networks, and IoT systems, among others [29].

Among the most common network characteristics that impact the network slicing process, we can mention delay-aware network slicing like in 5G deployments [30], quality of service (QoS) aware network slicing [25], energy-aware network slicing [31], and, in general, application-dependent and multi-domain network slicing [32].

Network Slicing Technology - Market and Trends

- ◆ NS most relevant market is 5G/6G:
 - ISPs, Telecommunication companies, experimental networks, health systems, and other
- ◆ Other NS market business:
 - ISPs, Telecommunication companies, and experimental networks
- ◆ Characteristics impacting the NS process:
 - Delay-aware network slicing like in 5G deployments, quality of service (QoS) aware network slicing, energy-aware network slicing, and, in general, application-dependent and multi-domain network slicing
- ◆ Machine learning (ML) is being extensively adopted by NS architectures

EDN Asia, "Understanding software-defined-radios and -networks in 5G architectures," Mar. 30, 2022. <https://www.ednasia.com/understanding-software-defined-radios-and-networks-in-5g-architectures/> (accessed Apr. 05, 2023).

K. Abbas, M. Afaq, T. Ahmed Khan, A. Rafiq, and W.-C. Song, "Slicing the Core Network and Radio Access Network Domains through Intent-Based Networking for 5G Networks," *Electronics*, vol. 9, no. 10, Art. no. 10, Oct. 2020, doi: [10.3390/electronics9101710](https://doi.org/10.3390/electronics9101710).

Fig. 8. Network Slicing Technology

9 NETWORK SLICING AND RESOURCE ALLOCATION

The network slicing process orchestrates resources and uses virtualization to allocate resources [33].

Current and future network slicing deployments use resources coming from multiple providers encompassing multiple technologies like IoT, unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV), and others:

- Resources belong to one or multiple providers (ISPs, Cloud, Content Providers, others);
- Resource provisioning with single or multidomain setup; and
- Multiple technologies are potentially involved in the slice resource allocation process (VMs, IoT, Radio Access Networks, others).

Fig. 9. Network Slicing and Resource Allocation

10 NETWORK SLICING REFERENCE ARCHITECTURES

There is a significant number of state-of-art network slicing research projects and standardization initiatives launched recently such as SFI2 (Slicing Future Internet Infrastructures) [34] [33], NECOS (Novel Enablers for Cloud Slicing) [35], SELFNET [36] and MATILDA [37]. Standardization initiatives include the IETF (Internet Engineering Task Force) [38], 3GPP (3rd Generation Partnership Project) [28], ITU (ITU-T - Telecommunication Standardization) [39], ETSI (European Telecommunications Standards Institute) [40] and ONF (Open Networking Foundation) [41]. Network slicing surveys are [23] [24] [42] [43] [44] [45].

These initiatives focus on distinct technical aspects, architectures, and slicing strategies, and all require communication slices to operate and manage the provided functionalities [7].

The network slicing architecture functionalities (resource marketplace, resource broker, resource orchestrator, slice instantiation, slice monitoring, and others) are distributed in terms of the domains participating in the deployment and depend on the proposed architecture and the deployed functional blocks of the network slicing architecture (SELFNET, NECOS, SFI2, MATILDA, other).

Network Slicing Architectures

- ◆ NS architectures for Resource Allocation
- ◆ Various NS architectures are available with distinct focuses
- ◆ Example: SFI2 NS architecture
 - Multidomain
 - Multi-technology
 - Experimental Network integration focus (FIBRE, CloudNext, 5GINFIRE, FUTEBOL, FIWARE, ...)
 - AI-native architecture

Fig. 10. Network Slicing Reference Architectures

11 THE COMMUNICATION SLICE FOR NETWORK SLICING (1)

A communication slice¹ is a set of communication resources used in the slicing process. It holds resources like links, optical slots, virtual private networks (VPNs), and other communication facilities necessary to provide the exchange of information among logical slices, and architectural slicing entities and for supporting the slicing process functionalities.

The communication slices and their allocated communication resources are essential in slicing architectures for resource orchestration and allocation, virtual network function (VNF) deployment, and slice operation functionalities. The communication slices provide the communications capabilities required to support slice operation, SLA guarantees, and QoS/ QoE application requirements [7].

For the scope of this discussion aiming at the communication slice model and deployment understanding, it is essential to conceptualize the vision of a *slice* as a component and product of the slicing process.

We define a slice as a specific resource, service, function, or set of resources, services, and functions virtualized, shared, and grouped using any software or hardware facility. The slice with its resources, services, and functions physically reside in nodes or another physical or virtual deployment in domains [7].

As such, slice resource examples are virtual machines, virtual switches with hosts deployed with OpenFlow, chunks of bandwidth belonging to a physical link, slots of a fiber EON deployment, LSP MPLS connections, shared spectrum in 5G radio access networks (RAN), and others. Slice function and service examples are virtual network functions (VNFs) deployed over a network providing specific services or facilities to the user.

A slice resulting from the NS process encompasses resources, services, and functions with the necessary communication resources to interconnect them inside domains and between domains.

The Communication Resource Issue for Network Slicing

- ◆ The allocation of resources for network slicing is addressed by the research community with a reasonable gap in terms of communication slices
- ◆ Network slicing deployment implies multiple alternatives for using the communication slice: intradomain and interdomain

Fig. 11. Network Slicing Communication Slice

1. A specialized slice that provides communication services among network slicing entities

12 THE COMMUNICATION SLICE FOR NETWORK SLICING (2)

In order to allow the execution of the network slicing process and functionalities in any deployed slicing architecture, it is necessary to allocate communication resources allowing communication among the entities involved in the slicing process. Furthermore, once the slice is deployed, communication resources are also necessary to support the communication requirements of the applications running (slice operation).

The slicing process may involve single or multiple domains (D_x, \dots, D_z). Each domain is generically configured by a single or a set of nodes (n_i, \dots, n_j) hosting resources and domains that are interconnected by communication resources.

A *communication slice* is then defined as a set of communication resources orchestrated and allocated between slices, nodes, network-slicing entities, and domains. As such, the domain nodes (n_i, \dots, n_j) hosting resources and domains are interconnected by communication slices (C_x, \dots, C_y).

We identify two types of communication slices that are orchestrated and deployed with distinct configurations and characteristics:

- Intradomain communication slices; and
- Interdomain communication slices.

The Communication Resource Issue for Network Slicing

- ◆ Inside a domain NS allocated resources are physically located at distinct nodes of the domain and need communication slices among nodes
- ◆ Network slicing also requires communication slices to be deployed to interconnect domains whit multidomain NS

Fig. 12. Network Slicing Communication Slice - Intradomain Scenario

13 THE NS COMMUNICATION SLICE - INTERDOMAIN SCENARIO

In NS infrastructures composed of network domains, a gateway concentrates all communications between distinct domains.

The objective of a network slicing interdomain communication model is to formally structure and capture the needs in terms of communications for the slicing process. It also allows the identification of parameters leading to the optimization of the resource allocation process [7].

A set of assumptions in the context of network slicing interdomain communications allows modeling and problem formulation [7]:

- Each network domain is SDN-compatible;
- Each network domain gateway GW_{D_i} is an SDN-enabled switch whose programmed behavior is to route packets between domains;
- Each network domain implements monitoring mechanisms to collect performance monitoring parameters;
- All intradomain and interdomain links are configurable in terms of allocated resources; and
- All network domains support network resource identification and have capabilities for resource allocation.

Network Slicing and Communication Slice

- ◆ The types of communication slices for network slicing:
 - ◆ Intradomain communication slices
 - ◆ Interdomain communication slices

Fig. 13. Network Slicing Communication Slice - Interdomain Scenario

14 THE NS COMMUNICATION SLICE - INTRADOMAIN SCENARIO

Inside a domain NS allocated resources are physically located at distinct nodes of the domain and need communication slices among nodes.

Network slicing architectures, projects, and initiatives address the conceptual and analytical modeling of the basic structures and functionalities that compose the slicing process and, to the best of our knowledge, do not address the conceptual and analytical modeling of communication slices.

Network Slicing and Communication Slice

- ◆ The types of communication slices for network slicing:
 - ◆ Intradomain communication slices
 - ◆ Interdomain communication slices

Fig. 14. Network Slicing Communication Slice - Intradomain Scenario

15 INTERDOMAIN COMMUNICATION SLICE OPTIMIZATION WITH SARSA AGENT

As an example of interdomain communication slice optimization, consider that a SARSA agent controls the queue flushing transmission rates of a link between domains to guarantee the performance parameters defined by the manager while sharing unused resources.

The slice communication queues (Q_i) in this example are configured as follows: i) Three queues corresponding to three performance parameters controlled by the agent; ii) Each configured queue threshold (Th_i) corresponds to the performance parameter assigned to the queue and served to packets generated by sliced resources with this requirement; and iii) Each queue Q_i has two states: below threshold (BT) and above threshold (AT) [7].

The actions defined for the queues are to increase the transmission rate, reduce the transmission rate, and do nothing. Each executed state/action has a defined reward.

The SARSA agent and communication slice parameters and initial conditions for running are as follows [7]:

- Agent configuration parameters: i) Epsilon-greedy policy $\epsilon = 8\%$; ii) Learning rate $\alpha = 20\%$; and iii) Discount factor $\gamma = 80\%$
- Other parameters are: i) Threshold limit (triggers agent action) = 50%; ii) Agent actions: bandwidth increased or reduced by 10%; iii) the Maximum number of attempts = 500; and iv) Queue priorities are: p_1, p_2 and p_3 with $p_1 > p_2 > p_3$.

The simulation presented in [7] shows the optimization results achieved.

Network Slicing and the Communication Slice Optimization

- ◆ The communication slices optimization is addressed with machine learning
- ◆ Example: how to share communication resources between different slices considering the performance requirement (e.g.: QoS) requirements of each slice

→ Target is an efficient communication slice using machine learning

Fig. 15. Communication Slice Optimization with SARSA Agent

16 WHY DO WE NEED SOFTWARE-DEFINED NETWORKING FOR NETWORK SLICING?

Software-defined networking (SDN) allows, in summary, the deployment of programmable networks with great flexibility [46].

SDN allows dynamic network configuration, operation, and management and, as such, is a crucial enabler supporting the deployment of infrastructures for new stringent applications and systems like network slicing [47].

Currently, SDN uses OpenFlow protocol as the most used interface to SDN-capable equipment.

In summary, our point is that network infrastructures are evolving to a more dynamic and flexible operation and management approach, and, for that, SDN is a suitable solution that brings various benefits to the deployed network

Why do we need Software-defined Networking for Network Slicing?

- ◆ Software-defined networking (SDN) allows, in summary, the creation and deployment of programmable networks
- ◆ SDN uses a logically centralized controller to program network equipment using a well know interface protocol like Openflow
- ◆ SDN allows a **dynamically configurable network infrastructure**

Our point is that network infrastructures are evolving to a more dynamic and flexible operation and management approach and, for that, SDN is a suitable solution that brings various benefits to the deployed network.

Fig. 16. Software-defined Networking

17 SDN AS AN ENABLER FOR NETWORK SLICING

SDN provides an accessible and easy-to-learn platform for network deployment.

SDN allows a reasonable monitoring infrastructure to evaluate the performance of the physical and virtual infrastructures.

SDN allows the management of diverse architectural models with large-scale configurations in a controllable manner [48].

SDN as an Enabler for Network Slicing

- ◆ SDN provides an accessible and easy-to-learn platform for network deployment
- ◆ SDN allows reasonable monitoring of the performance of the physical and virtual network infrastructures
- ◆ SDN allows the management of multiple architectural models in large-scale network configurations in a controllable manner

Fig. 17. SDN Enabler

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